

A HYBRID RELIABILITY FRAMEWORK FOR SPARE PART OPTIMISATION UNDER UNCERTAINTY OF MARINE VESSEL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Effective spare part management relies heavily on accurate reliability assessment. However, in new or complex systems, historical failure data are often limited, making traditional probabilistic reliability models inadequate. This paper proposes a hybrid reliability framework that integrates conventional reliability theory with fuzzy logic to address both aleatory (random) and epistemic (lack of knowledge) uncertainties. The approach combines crisp failure rate estimation using exponential distributions with fuzzy reliability modelling using the triangular fuzzy number (TFN) methodology and fuzzy logic to support dynamic decision-making for a maintenance plan. The degree of membership functions is derived from the TFN and provides the operator with a decision-making tool, enabling robust reliability estimation even in data-scarce environments. The model is applied to ten marine vessels, analysing systems in the engine room. Results show that the hybrid approach provides a more realistic and flexible reliability assessment compared to conventional methods alone, particularly for components with sparse failure records. The integration of fuzzy logic enables sensitivity analysis and enhances decision-making in maintenance planning. This work lays the foundation for a more comprehensive spare-part prioritisation framework, especially when uncertainty dominates operational decisions.

Keywords: conventional reliability, fuzzy reliability, data scarcity, aleatory uncertainty, epistemic uncertainty, triangle fuzzy number, fuzzy logic

INTRODUCTION

Conventional probabilistic approaches are common in the analysis of the reliability of complex engineering systems. However, they require quantitative historical failure data for determining reliability characteristics [1]. Obtaining failure data can be challenging due to insufficient data, environmental changes, or the introduction of new components [2]. When focusing on hardware reliability, there are two approaches for determining equipment reliability: the physical approach and the actuarial approach. In the physical approach, the strength S and the load L are modelled as random variables. A failure occurs when the load exceeds the strength. The reliability, R , is defined as the probability that the strength exceeds the load [3].

Spare parts planning is also crucial in complex systems.

Components of a pump, for example, must be ready during the repair or replacement of parts. Reliability analysis will support the decision on both the quantity and selection of spare parts to be held in inventory, as well as on procurement and delivery strategies, specifically, whether parts should be procured and delivered only a few days before maintenance activities or positioned at the supplier's location and dispatched to the site only when required. This has to take into account the transportation period. For special spare parts made to order, which typically have an extended delivery period, the decision on when to procure is crucial so the machine does not fail before the spare part arrives. Therefore, integrating reliability analysis into supply chain management helps support spare part planning decisions.

An appropriate approximation method to address the current problem and challenges in supply chain management is to focus on the spare parts supply chain by integrating reliability results from part failures with spare parts requirement forecasting [4]-[7]. The conventional reliability method requires a large amount of historical data. It is only feasible for the operator to obtain accurate historical data when a system has been running for an extended period of time. Furthermore, the historical data acquired must be sufficiently large to yield accurate results.

As for the fuzzy reliability method, a new plant can utilise it, as it does not require historical data and only requires expert opinion. However, the lack of expert knowledge would lead to insufficient input, hindering better results. The operator's lack of expertise in assessing failure probability provides questionable results due to poor-quality input assessment [8].

In the research presented by Swain et al. [9], which analyses microgrid dependability reliability using a Markov process, the authors indicate that the data used are both restricted and imprecise, and that uncertainties are accounted for, thereby introducing fuzzy sets into their studies. When axiomatic fuzzy set theory is incorporated into stress-strength inference, it enables more precise studies of the underlying systems [10]. The proposed fuzzy approach builds membership functions for system characteristics and then extracts a family of conventional crisp intervals from the fuzzy system to represent the desired system characteristics [11]. When membership functions govern system characteristics, more information is provided for management use. Additionally, as the redundant system is extended to a fuzzy environment, general repairable systems are represented more accurately. The analytic results are more useful for designers and practitioners.

Due to the inaccuracy and unavailability of data for distribution components, a reliability assessment of the distribution system is introduced, based on historical data and probabilistic methods, utilising fuzzy logic as an efficient method to handle the uncertainty in reliability inputs [12].

This paper proposes a hybrid reliability framework that integrates conventional probabilistic methods with fuzzy logic to address both aleatory and epistemic uncertainties in spare parts optimisation. The approach is validated

using failure data from offshore vessels, demonstrating its effectiveness in data-scarce environments. By combining crisp failure rate estimation with fuzzy reliability modelling, the framework provides a robust decision-making tool for maintenance planning, offering significant improvements over traditional reliability methods in reliability engineering applications and spare part optimisation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The management of spare parts is a critical aspect of maintenance operations, particularly in industries where equipment reliability and uptime are paramount, such as power distribution systems, aviation, and manufacturing. Effective spare part management ensures that critical components are available when needed, minimising downtime and operational disruptions. However, the challenge lies in identifying and prioritising the most critical components for maintenance and spare part provisioning, especially when historical failure data is scarce or uncertain. This research addresses this challenge by proposing an integrated approach that combines conventional reliability theory with fuzzy set theory, leveraging the strengths of both methodologies to enhance decision-making in spare part management.

Reliability analysis of repairable systems is commonly conducted under the assumption of minimal repair, resulting in non homogeneous Poisson process models [13]. In repairable systems, a specific component may be refurbished, depending on its state of failure. Component reconditioning may restore the component to as-good-as-new or, at the other end, to as-bad-as-old, a state equivalent to minimal repair [14].

Traditional reliability models, which assume systems and their components can be in one of two possible states, either working perfectly or completely failed. A multi-state system is one in which systems can execute their intended tasks at multiple levels of efficiency or performance, ranging from perfectly functioning to completely failed states [15]. A non-repairable system with multiple and cyclic mission sequences, whose components exhibit multi-mode failures, for example, a valve system with two failure modes can not only fail to close when required to do so. However, it can also fail to open when required to do so [16].

When designing the plant system, it is helpful to perform reliability analysis to support decision-making, particularly when considering the combination of a repairable and a non-repairable system within a complex system. This combination is typically beyond the scope of assumptions when studied. A complex plant system is often assumed to have a single-sided approach, whereby the entire system is either considered non-repairable or repairable. In real-world situations, systems typically include both repairable and non-repairable components [17].

Jia et al. [18] proposed an analytical method based on a multi-state decision diagram for reliability analysis, accounting for the successful activation probabilities of warm-standby units in a multi-state, non-repairable power generation system. The work offers a flexible application to multi-state generation systems with arbitrary state transition time distributions rather than being limited to systems with exponential distributions. Some researchers combine a reliability model for non-repairable systems. For example, Zhai et al. [19] combine a new model, the aggregated binary decision diagram (ABDD), with non-repairable phased-mission systems (PMSs) subject to dynamic demand. The proposed method then incorporates fault-level coverage into the ABDD mode. The combined method is said to be more computationally efficient than the existing method.

Future work is suggested to focus on the ABDD construction procedure based on fault tree analysis, as well as on warm, cold, and mixed standby modes. Prior to that, Chen [20] identified the failure mechanism dependence or failure process dependence effect as competition, trigger, acceleration, inhibition, and accumulation. Based on the fundamental rule of physics of failure, the author proposed a decoupling process for these dependence effects. The system reliability evaluation method for incorporating those dependence-failure processes was investigated for a non-repairable system. The author found a correlation among the failure mechanisms, including competition, trigger, acceleration, inhibition, and accumulation. Their work is currently being applied to reliability prediction of electronic devices in aviation and to performing maintenance actions for systems in the aerospace area.

The fuzzy methods for evaluating the reliability of complex systems made the qualitative approach for

assessing system reliability effective. Additionally, experts are more comfortable justifying the likelihood of event failure using linguistic terms that capture uncertainty rather than expressing judgments in quantitative terms [1]. The mathematical basis of the computational model of fuzzy reliability and probability can be computed using the conventional probability method via a mathematical transition. Then, a numerical algorithm is provided that can be applied to compute the fuzzy reliability of a component in a complex system [21].

Reliability-Based Decision Making

Reliability theory has long been a cornerstone of maintenance and spare part management. Conventional reliability approaches rely on probability theory, which requires substantial historical failure data to estimate failure rates accurately and predict component lifespans [22]. However, in many real-world scenarios, especially in newly deployed systems or systems with low failure rates, such data may be insufficient or unavailable. This limitation undermines the effectiveness of conventional reliability methods, as they cannot adequately account for uncertainty in the absence of robust historical data [23]. To address this issue, fuzzy set theory has emerged as a powerful tool for handling uncertainty in reliability analysis. Fuzzy reliability approaches allow decision-makers to model and analyse systems even when failure data is incomplete or imprecise. By incorporating fuzzy logic, these methods can represent the inherent vagueness and ambiguity in failure rates, providing a more flexible and realistic framework for reliability assessment. However, while fuzzy reliability methods excel in handling uncertainty, they often lack the precision of conventional reliability approaches when sufficient data is available. Therefore, there is a need to integrate both conventional and fuzzy reliability theories to create a more comprehensive and adaptable framework for spare part management. Komal [24] addressed this limitation by proposing a fuzzy reliability approach that utilises the best available failure data, even when it is incomplete or imprecise. By employing triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs) to represent the fuzziness of failure rates, Komal's approach provides a more flexible and realistic framework for reliability analysis. However, while this method is effective in handling uncertainty, it does not fully leverage the strengths of conventional reliability theory when sufficient data is available.

The existing literature highlights the strengths and limitations of both conventional and fuzzy reliability approaches. Conventional reliability methods are precise and effective when sufficient historical data is available, but they struggle in scenarios with limited or uncertain data. On the other hand, fuzzy reliability methods excel in handling uncertainty but may lack precision when robust data is available. This dichotomy creates a research gap, the need for an integrated approach that combines the precision of conventional reliability theory with the flexibility of fuzzy set theory to address the challenges of spare part management in diverse scenarios.

METHODS

Probability Reliability

As discussed earlier in the introduction, two approaches are used to determine equipment reliability. The approaches are physical and actuarial. In the physical approach, the strength S is modelled as a random variable, and the load L is a random variable. A failure occurs as soon as the load is greater than the strength. The reliability, R , is defined as the probability that the strength is greater than the load [3].

Failure events can be denoted as those when the load, L , exceeds the strength, S . When we assume the time to failure, T , is continuously distributed with a probability density function $f(t)$ and a distribution function $F(t)$:

$$F(t) = Pr(T \leq t) = \int_0^t f(u)du \quad \text{for, } t > 0 \quad (1)$$

If a random variable X is assumed to take a particular value, the probability distribution is used to define that value. In this case, it is represented by a continuous

random variable. Therefore, the range of possible values of these random variables spans a continuum of real numbers. A probability density function $f(x)$ is used to describe the probability distribution [25] of the variable under consideration, X . The probability density function $f(x)$ is illustrated in Figure 1.

The probability of X is in the interval of a and b in the integral of $f(x)$ from a to b of the probability density function. The probability is shown in Figure 2.

The area under the probability density function $f(x)$ can be defined as:

$$P\{a \leq X \leq b\} = \int_a^b f(x)dx \quad (2)$$

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a continuous random variable X is defined as:

$$P(a \leq X \leq b) = F(b) - F(a) = \int_a^b f(x)dx \quad (3)$$

where, $F(b) - F(a)$ equals the integral of the probability density function $f(x)$ from a to b .

Table 1 Some reliability indices for a non-repairable system

Reliability Indices	Expressions
Mean time to failure	$MTTF = \frac{1}{\lambda}$
Reliability	$R(t) = e^{-\lambda t}$

Integration of Conventional (Probability) and Fuzzy Reliability

The study begins with an understanding of the concept of reliability engineering. This paper focused on conventional and fuzzy reliability engineering and

Figure 1 Comparison of the (a) probability density function and (b) area under the curve

Figure 2 CDF showing the probability $P(a \leq X \leq b)$ as the difference

their applications. The integration of both and its application to spare part optimisation is then produced. The workflow diagram is shown in Figure 3.

The failure rate of a component or piece of equipment is calculated based on the number of failures per year. Using the exponential distribution, the reliability of a component or piece of equipment is determined. The fuzzy failure rate is then established using the Komal [24] method for a TFN with a 15% spread.

Then, the main criteria are tested for their relations using the fuzzy relations method. The relation between the two main criteria is determined, and the relation between those relations and another main criterion is also tested. The fuzzy failure rate implication will be determined using rule-based fuzzy logic.

The methodology for spare part management and optimisation begins with the critical step of identifying the component’s failure rate. This involves collecting historical failure data from various sources, such as maintenance logs, operational records, and industry databases. The data is then analysed using statistical methods such as mean time to failure (MTTF) or exponential analysis to estimate the failure rate, λ . These methods provide a quantitative measure of how often a component is likely to fail under normal operating conditions. However, it is essential to validate the calculated failure rate by comparing it with industry benchmarks or similar components to ensure its accuracy.

Additionally, uncertainties or variations in the failure rate must be documented, as factors such as

Figure 3 Flowchart of fuzzy logic-based spare part optimisation incorporating dynamic membership functions

operational conditions, environmental influences, and component age can significantly affect failure behaviour. For instance, a component operating in a high-temperature environment may exhibit a higher failure rate than the same component in a controlled setting. By accounting for these variables, the failure rate becomes a more reliable metric for further analysis.

A comprehensive rule base of 45 fuzzy rules (3 rules per system) was constructed. The rule weight for each system was calculated based on its normalised failure rate, reflecting its relative contribution to overall engine room risk.

The system/equipment will first undergo normalisation, where the weight W_i for a specific component i is its individual failure rate λ_i divided by the sum of all failure rates λ_{total} . This ensures systems with higher failure rates have a greater influence on the final output:

$$Weight_i = \frac{\lambda_{crisp_i}}{\sum \lambda_{crisp}} \quad (4)$$

$$W_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{\sum_{k=1}^{15} \lambda_k}$$

Once the failure rate is established, it is translated into a fuzzy failure rate to account for inherent uncertainties and data imprecision. This result is achieved by defining the fuzzy failure rate using TFNs, which provide a mathematical framework for representing vague or uncertain information. The membership function for the fuzzy failure rate is determined either by expert judgment or by the distribution of historical data. For example, if historical data shows that the failure rate of a component typically ranges between 0.05 and 0.1 failures per hour, the fuzzy failure rate can be represented as a TFN with these values as its lower and upper bounds. The fuzzy failure rate is then validated with domain experts to ensure it accurately represents the component's failure behaviour. This step is crucial because it bridges the gap between precise numerical data and the real-world uncertainties that often accompany failure rate estimation.

A fuzzy inference system (FIS) is developed to model the impact of the fuzzy failure rate on each criterion. Fuzzy rules (IF-THEN statements) are defined to map the failure rate to the criteria. For example, a rule might state, "IF the failure rate is high, THEN reliability is low," indicating that components with higher failure rates will lower the system's reliability. Fuzzy

reasoning is performed to evaluate these implications, and the model is validated with real-world data. This step ensures that the fuzzy failure rate is effectively integrated into the decision-making process, providing a more nuanced understanding of its impact on spare part management.

To account for the dynamic nature of failure rates, a dynamic failure rate is generated based on TFN and the maintenance plan. The maintenance plan, including preventive maintenance intervals and corrective actions, is incorporated into the fuzzy failure rate model. For example, if a component undergoes preventive maintenance every 500 hours, its failure rate might decrease temporarily before gradually increasing again. The TFNs are updated to reflect these changes over time, and simulations are conducted to assess the impact of different maintenance scenarios on reliability and spare part requirements. The dynamic failure rate model is validated using real-world failure data to ensure its accuracy and applicability. This step is critical because it allows decision-makers to anticipate changes in failure rates and adjust their strategies accordingly.

The fuzzification converts crisp values using membership functions for TFNs that span 15% below and above the bounds [24], where the membership function $\mu = 1$ is derived from the probability of failure rate from historical data. The fuzzy values are divided into three membership functions: low, medium, and high failure rates. Then, the fuzzy rule IF-THEN is created and inserted into the MATLAB Simulink application, which consists of all 15 input variables for the engine room equipment and system. The output for this is the overall engine room reliability and the percentage of spare part requirement. The FIS for this method uses the Mamdani method. The Mamdani method provides better inference when linguistic input variables are involved, producing a fuzzy output.

Figure 4 shows the input variables for the TFNs and the output reliability and spare part requirement, which are populated in the MATLAB Simulink environment.

Throughout the process, additional considerations such as data collection and validation, sensitivity analysis, stakeholder involvement, and the use of software tools are emphasised to enhance the robustness and applicability of the methodology. Data collection

Figure 4 TFN for (a) air compressor, (b) cooling system, and (c) electrical equipment

and validation ensure that the inputs are accurate and reliable, while sensitivity analysis assesses the impact of changes in failure rates, criteria weights, or maintenance plans on the final rankings. Stakeholder involvement ensures the methodology aligns with organisational goals and priorities, while software tools such as MATLAB, Python, or specialised fuzzy-logic software automate calculations and improve accuracy. Documentation and reporting are also prioritised to ensure transparency and provide a clear basis for decision-making. This comprehensive approach provides a systematic, effective framework for spare part management and optimisation that addresses real-world complexities and uncertainties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The foundation of this study lies in the analysis of defect reports collected from offshore vessels. These vessels were utilised primarily for crew transportation to and from offshore platforms and have been systematically documenting operational defects from 2018 to 2025, providing a comprehensive dataset for evaluation. The vessel crew manually entered data into a structured defect reporting system to ensure that all technical, mechanical, and operational issues were recorded in a standardised format. This approach not only facilitates consistency in data collection but also enhances the reliability of subsequent analyses.

The dataset encompasses a wide range of defect types, including engine failures, electrical malfunctions, structural damages, and safety equipment deficiencies, among others. Each entry includes critical details such as the date of occurrence, defect description, severity level, corrective actions taken, and the personnel responsible for reporting. This granularity ensures

that the analysis can be conducted at multiple levels, ranging from trend identification, such as recurring defects, to root-cause analysis.

One of the key strengths of this dataset is its longitudinal nature, spanning seven years (2018–2025). This extended timeframe enables the examination of seasonal variations, the effectiveness of maintenance over time, and the impact of operational changes on defect frequency. Moreover, since the data is sourced from 10 different vessels, it provides an opportunity to compare performance across individual units and identify whether certain vessels exhibit higher defect rates due to age, usage patterns, or maintenance practices.

However, while the dataset is robust, certain limitations must be acknowledged. Since crew members manually enter the reports, there is a risk of human error in defect classification or of omitting minor issues that were resolved informally. Despite these constraints, the dataset remains highly valuable for identifying broad trends, operational inefficiencies, and areas requiring targeted maintenance improvements. This study does not account for the human error factor.

The forthcoming analysis will leverage this dataset to extract meaningful insights that can enhance vessel reliability, optimise maintenance schedules, and improve safety protocols. The system will be analysed based on the importance of the main criteria, then ranked. The organisation can plan and allocate its budget to spare parts based on the ranking.

Table 2 presents the total number of failures and the corresponding failure rate for crew boats over the 7-year period (2018-2025). The equipment and

Table 2 Failure data for shipboard engine room system

Equipment/System	No. of Failures	Failure Rate (per year)
Air Compressor (AC)	6	0.0857
Cooling Systems (CS)	14	0.2000
Electrical Equipment (EE)	91	1.3000
Electrical Instruments (EI)	2	0.0286
Emergency Shutdown System (ESDS)	2	0.0286
Engine Room Ventilation Systems (ERVS)	25	0.3571
Fuel Oil System (FOS)	70	1.0000
Main Engines (ME)	324	4.6286
Oil Dispersant System (ODS)	22	0.3143
Oily Water Separator (OWS)	8	0.1143
Power Generation Systems (PGS)	145	2.0714
Pumps (P)	18	0.2571
Reduction Gear (RG)	16	0.2286
Steering Gear (SG)	27	0.3857
Valves (V)	5	0.0714

systems in the engine room involve both mechanical and electrical components.

Then the failure rate is fuzzified using the method proposed by Komal [24], with a failure rate limit of 15% for the lower and upper values. Furthermore, a fuzzy failure rate is determined using a membership function, where $\mu = 1$ represents the probability of failure rate, and $\mu = 0$ represents the limit value of the fuzzy triangle

at 15%, as shown in Table 3. Furthermore, the TFNs plotted for individual equipment/systems are shown in Figures 4a to 8c.

Below are the fuzzy rules. The failure rate is normalised across the system/equipment probability of failure to establish a common basis for weighting. At the end of every system/equipment rule, this determines the significance of the failure rate for each system/equipment. The weight of every rule is derived empirically using the calculation in Equation 4. These calculated weights are central to the framework’s decision-making logic, representing the significance of each component’s failure rate relative to the entire engine room system. The FIS, shown in Figure 9, aggregates all 45 weighted rules, synthesising the individual fuzzy failure rates into a consolidated output. This output is defined as the system/equipment’s precedence, providing a quantifiable, ranked metric. This ranking mechanism directly facilitates prioritisation, allowing management to objectively identify the most critical components, those with the highest weighted impact on reliability, and strategically allocate the spare part budget and inventory accordingly.

1. If (AC is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.005654)
2. If (AC is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.005654)

Table 3 Failure rate analysis for engine room systems

Equipment/System	15% lowerbound	Probability Failure Rate	15% upperbound
Air Compressor (AC)	0.0729	0.0857	0.0986
Cooling Systems (CS)	0.17	0.2	0.23
Electrical Equipment (EE)	1.105	1.3	1.495
Electrical Instruments (EI)	0.0243	0.0286	0.0329
Emergency Shutdown System (ESDS)	0.0243	0.0286	0.0329
Engine Room Ventilation Systems (ERVS)	0.3036	0.3571	0.4107
Fuel Oil System (FOS)	0.85	1.0	1.15
Main Engines (ME)	3.9343	4.6286	5.3229
Oil Dispersant System (ODS)	0.2671	0.3143	0.3614
Oily Water Separator (OWS)	0.0971	0.1143	0.1314
Power Generation Systems (PGS)	1.7607	2.0714	2.3821
Pumps (P)	0.2186	0.2571	0.2957
Reduction Gear (RG)	0.1943	0.2286	0.2629
Steering Gear (SG)	0.3279	0.3857	0.4436
Valves (V)	0.0607	0.0714	0.0821

Figure 5 TFNs for (a) electrical instruments, (b) emergency shutdown, and (c) ventilation

Figure 6 TFNs for (a) fuel oil system, (b) main engine, and (c) oil dispersant

Figure 7 TFNs for (a) oily water separator, (b) power generation, and (c) pumps

3. If (AC is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.005654)
4. If (CS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.018025)
5. If (CS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.018025)
6. If (CS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.018025)
7. If (EE is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.11776)
8. If (EE is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.11776)
9. If (EE is low) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.11776)
10. If (EI is high) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.0003826)
11. If (EI is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.0003826)
12. If (EI is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.0003826)

Figure 8 TFNs for (a) reduction gear, (b) steering gear, and (c) valves

Figure 9 Fuzzy rules presented in MATLAB Simulink environment

- | | |
|---|---|
| 13. If (ESDS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.0003826) | 22. If (ME is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.42512) |
| 14. If (ESDS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.0003826) | 23. If (ME is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.42512) |
| 15. If (ESDS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.0003826) | 24. If (ME is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.42512) |
| 16. If (ERVS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.030778) | 25. If (ODS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.028483) |
| 17. If (ERVS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.030778) | 26. If (ODS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.028483) |
| 18. If (ERVS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.030778) | 27. If (ODS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.028483) |
| 19. If (FOS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.089955) | 28. If (OWS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.010118) |
| 20. If (FOS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.089955) | 29. If (OWS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.010118) |
| 21. If (FOS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.089955) | 30. If (OWS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.010118) |

31. If (PGS is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.18824)
32. If (PGS is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.18824)
33. If (PGS is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.18824)
34. If (P is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.023254)
35. If (P is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.023254)
36. If (P is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.023254)
37. If (RG is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.020576)
38. If (RG is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.020576)
39. If (RG is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.020576)
40. If (SG is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.035115)
41. If (SG is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.035115)
42. If (SG is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.035115)
43. If (V is low) then (Reliability is high) (Spare-Part is low) (0.0061642)
44. If (V is medium) then (Reliability is medium) (Spare-Part is medium) (0.0061642)
45. If (V is high) then (Reliability is Low) (Spare-Part is high) (0.0061642)

CONCLUSION

This study addressed limitations of conventional reliability models in handling uncertainty and incomplete data by developing a hybrid framework that integrates conventional reliability and fuzzy set theory, aiming to enhance spare part management in reliability-critical industries. The research developed a hybrid reliability index that combines conventional and fuzzy reliability, enabling nuanced assessments under varying data conditions. The framework is effective in both data-rich and data-poor environments, with case studies demonstrating improvements in maintenance planning, reduced unplanned downtime, and enhanced spare part availability, as validated by failure data from offshore vessels. By combining crisp failure rate estimation with fuzzy reliability modelling, it provides a robust decision-making tool, offering significant improvements over

traditional reliability methods in reliability engineering and spare part optimisation. The framework integrates probabilistic and fuzzy logic approaches, bridging reliability modelling and spare part optimisation in a systematic, scalable way. Limitations include the reliance on expert input in fuzzy modelling, which may introduce subjective bias, and the focus on case studies of maritime systems, necessitating broader industrial validation. Future research could integrate real-time sensor data and machine learning for dynamic reliability assessments, employ methods such as the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) to manage interdependencies and decision scalability, and combine reliability analysis with cost models, including total cost of ownership or downtime costs, for comprehensive spare part decision-making. Expanding the framework for distributed decision-making in multi-agent environments and analysing failure data at the component level could further enhance results.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J.H. Purba, J. Lu, G. Zhang, and W. Pedrycz, "A Fuzzy Reliability Assessment of Basic Events of Fault Trees Through Qualitative Data Processing," *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, vol. 243, pp. 50–69, 2014.
- [2] J.H. Purba, "A Fuzzy-Based Reliability Approach to Evaluate Basic Events of Fault Tree Analysis for Nuclear Power Plant Probabilistic Safety Assessment," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 70, pp. 21–29, 2014.
- [3] M. Rausand and A. Høyland, *System Reliability Theory: Models, Statistical Methods, and Applications*, vol. 396. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2004.
- [4] B. Hellingrath and A.-K. Cordes, "Approach for Integrating Condition Monitoring Information and Forecasting Methods to Enhance Spare Parts Supply Chain Planning," *IFAC Proc. Vol.*, vol. 46, no. 7, pp. 17–22, 2013.
- [5] D. Espindola, E.M. Frazzon, B. Hellingrath, and C.E. Pereira, "Integrating Intelligent Maintenance Systems

- and Spare Parts Supply Chains," *IFAC Proc. Vol.*, vol. 45, no. 6, pp. 1017–1022, 2012.
- [6] T.R. da Silva, P. Saalman, A.-K. Cordes, A. Giacomolli, C.E. Pereira, and B. Hellingrath, "Integration Architecture of Intelligent Maintenance Systems and Spare Parts Supply Chain Planning," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 25, pp. 192–198, 2014.
- [7] B. Hellingrath, C.E. Pereira, D. Espindola, E.M. Frazzon, A.-K. Cordes, P. Saalman, and M. Zuccolotto, "On the Integration of Intelligent Maintenance and Spare Parts Supply Chain Management," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 983–988, 2015.
- [8] S. Rajakarunakaran, A. Maniram Kumar, and V.A. Prabhu, "Applications of Fuzzy Fault Tree Analysis and Expert Elicitation for Evaluation of Risks in LPG Refuelling Station," *J. Loss Prev. Process Ind.*, vol. 33, pp. 109–123, 2015.
- [9] K. Swain, M. Cherukuri, I. S. Samanta, A. Pati, J. Giri, A. Panigrahi, H. Qin, and S. Mallik, "Fuzzy Markov Model for the Reliability Analysis of Hybrid Microgrids," *Front. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 6, 2024.
- [10] E. Hussam, M.A. Sabry, M.M. Abd El-Raouf, and E.M. Almetwally, "Fuzzy vs. Traditional Reliability Model for Inverse Weibull Distribution," *Axioms*, vol. 12, no. 6, 2023.
- [11] S. Jamali and M.J. Bani, "Application of Fuzzy Assessing for Reliability Decision Making," 2017.
- [12] A. Shokrollahi, H. Sangrody, M. Motalleb, M. Rezaeiahari, E. Foruzan, and F. Hassanzadeh, "Reliability Assessment of Distribution System Using Fuzzy Logic for Modelling of Transformer and Line Uncertainties," 2017.
- [13] Z. G. Asfaw and B.H. Lindqvist, "Extending Minimal Repair Models for Repairable Systems: A Comparison of Dynamic and Heterogeneous Extensions of a Non-homogeneous Poisson Process," *Rel. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 140, pp. 53–58, 2015.
- [14] P.K. Chemweno, L. Pintelon, and P.N. Muchiri, "Evaluating the Impact of Spare Parts Pooling Strategy on the Maintenance of Unreliable Repairable Systems," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 989–994, 2015.
- [15] T. Jiang and Y. Liu, "Parameter Inference for Non-Repairable Multi-State System Reliability Models by Multi-Level Observation Sequences," *Rel. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, 2016.
- [16] Y. Li, L. Cui, and H. Yi, "Reliability of Non-Repairable Systems With Cyclic-Mission Switching and Multi-mode Failure Components," *J. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 17, pp. 126–138, 2016.
- [17] H. Zoufaghari, A.Z. Hamadani, and M.A. Ardakan, "Bi-Objective Redundancy Allocation Problem for a System With Mixed Repairable and Non-Repairable Components," *ISA Trans.*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 17–24, 2014.
- [18] H. Jia, Y. Ding, R. Peng, H. Liu, and Y. Song, "Reliability Assessment and Activation Sequence Optimisation of Non-Repairable Multi-State Generation Systems Considering Warm Standby," *Rel. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 195, p. 106736, 2020.
- [19] Q. Zhai, L. Xing, R. Peng, and J. Yang, "Aggregated Combinatorial Reliability Model for Non-Repairable Parallel Phased-Mission Systems," *Rel. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 176, pp. 242–250, 2018.
- [20] Y. Chen, L. Yang, C. Ye, and R. Kang, "Failure Mechanism Dependence and Reliability Evaluation of Non-Repairable System," *Rel. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 138, pp. 273–283, 2015.
- [21] Q. Jiang and C.-H. Chen, "A Numerical Algorithm of Fuzzy Reliability," *Rel. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 80, no. 3, pp. 299–307, 2003.
- [22] P.D.T. O'Connor and A. Kleyner, "Reliability mathematics," in *Practical Reliability Engineering*, 5th ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2011, ch. 2, doi: 10.1002/9781119961260.ch2.
- [23] W.B. Nelson, "Life Data Analysis and Probability Plotting," in *Applied Life Data Analysis*, Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2011, ch. 3, pp. 70–107.
- [24] Komal, D. Chang, and S.Y. Lee, "Fuzzy Reliability Analysis of Dual-Fuel Steam Turbine Propulsion System in LNG Carriers Considering Data Uncertainty," *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.*, vol. 23, pp. 148–164, 2015.
- [25] M. Lazzaroni, L. Cristaldi, L. Peretto, P. Rinaldi, and M. Catelani, "The concept of 'statistical' reliability," in *Reliability Engineering*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2011, ch. 2, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-20983-3_2.